

Studies in Silicic Acid Gels. Part IV. The Effect of Electrolytes on the Time of Setting of the Gel-forming Mixtures.

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It has been shown in Part II (Prasad and Hattiangadi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 898) that the process of setting of mixtures of solutions of sodium silicate and acidic ammonium acetate or acetic acid consists of three stages:

- (1) The formation of silicic acid by the interaction of acids with sodium silicate.
- (2) The formation of the colloidal solution of silicic acid.
- (3) The coagulation of the colloidal solution by the electrolytes liberated in the first reaction.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to examine the effect produced on the time of setting of the silicic acid gels by the addition of extra quantities of electrolytes to the gel-forming mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The effect of sodium and potassium salts of nitric, sulphuric, hydrochloric and acetic acids on the acid and alkaline gel-forming mixtures has been chiefly studied. The effect of bivalent and trivalent basic radicals could not be examined as most of these electrolytes reacted to give the corresponding insoluble silicates. The electrolytes used were Merck's "extra pure" chemicals.

The sodium silicate used was Na_2O , 2SiO_2 and a solution of 4 per cent. silica content was prepared as described in Part I (cf. Prasad and Hattiangadi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 653). It was observed during the course of this investigation that the nature of sodium silicate (cf. Harmann, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1155; 1926, 30, 359, 917) is very important in studying the process of gel-formation. A solution of 4 per cent. silica content of sodium silicate Na_2O , SiO_2 could not give rigid gels with ammonium acetate or acetic acid like Na_2O , 2SiO_2 even when the p_{H} of the reaction mix-

ture was 8.5—9. With Na_2O , SiO_2 , in fairly alkaline solutions, only a flaky precipitate was produced which settled to the bottom on standing. Highly alkaline solutions hardly showed any signs of coagulation even in course of weeks. Pyridine, which has been shown in Part III to accelerate the process of gelation tremendously, failed to produce a stiff gel in fairly alkaline solutions. A stiff gel is however obtained near the neutralisation point when the reaction mixture is just alkaline, that is, when the process of gelation is quickest and there is hardly any time for a possible peptisation of the coagulum formed. Of course, in acidic mixtures stiff vibrant gels with solutions of Na_2O , SiO_2 were easily obtained. Besides these deviations, the sample Na_2O , SiO_2 dissolved in water easily, the process of solution being highly endothermic, while Na_2O , 2SiO_2 and Na_2O , 2.33SiO_2 took a long time to give clear solutions and the absorption of heat during solution was negligible.

In the following, different amounts of 4*N*- and 2*N*-electrolytes were added to 5 c.c. of the acetic acid solution and this was mixed with 5 c.c. of the solution of sodium silicate (Na_2O , 2SiO_2). The time of setting was measured from the time—deflection curves (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*) and the results obtained are given in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=4$ per cent.
Concentration of acetic acid=0.8*N*.

Reaction acidic.

Electrolytes.	C.c. of 4 <i>N</i> -electrolytes in 10 c. c. of the mixtures.							
	0	0.5		1.0		1.25		
	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A	t (min.)	A
NaCl	57	5.5	42	6	32	6.5	29	7.0
KCl	57	5.5	36	6	24	7.5	20	8.0
NaNO_3	57	5.5	48	6	36	6.5	30	6.5
KNO_3	57	5.5	38	5	27	7.0	24	7.5
NaAc	57	5.5	39	6	32	7.0	30	7.5
KAc	57	5.5	34	7	25	7.5	28	7.5
Na_2SO_4	57	5.5	50	5.5	45	6.0	48	6.0

TABLE II.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4$ per cent.
 Concentration of acetic acid = $0.55N$.

Reaction alkaline.

C.c. of $2N$ -electrolytes in 10 c. c. of the mixtures.

<i>Electrolytes.</i>	<i>t</i> (min.)	C.c. of $2N$ -electrolytes in 10 c. c. of the mixtures.					
		0		1.0		2.5	
		<i>A</i>	<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>A</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>A</i>	
NaCl	22	9	3	20	45 sec.	30	
KCl	22	9	1½	24	Ppt.	—	
NaNO_3	22	9	3½	17	1 min.	26	
KNO_3	22	9	2	21	20 sec.	30	
NaAc	22	9	3	22	40 sec.	32	
KAc	22	9	1½	25	Ppt.	—	
Na_2SO_4	22	9	6	17	2 min.	22	

It will be seen from Tables I and II that the addition of extra quantities of electrolytes accelerates the gel-formation in the alkaline and the acid mixtures. Increasing quantities of the substances not only reduce the time of setting but also increase their opacity. It will further be seen that the size of the gel particles is different with different electrolytes and is not dependent upon the time of setting as shown in column A of the tables.

The effect of these substances on the pure dialysed sol of silicic acid was then examined and no evidence of coagulation could be detected. This observation is similar to that of Thomas Graham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1864, 17, 321) who found that acids were inactive towards a pure sol of silicic acid.

The pure dialysed sol was made alkaline and acidic by the addition of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid respectively. The effect of the addition of these electrolytes to these alkaline and acid sols was that a rapid coagulation took place in the former, while hardly any coagulation was observed in the latter. Pappada (*Gassetta*, 1905, 35, 78; *J. Chem. Soc., Abs.*, 1905, *ii*, 88, 987) also found that coagulants were rendered inactive in the presence of acids while coagulation was favoured in the presence of substances having a basic reaction and that the coagulating action of salts is intimately connected with the position of the metals in the periodic system.

Discussion of Results.

The addition of extra quantities of electrolytes to these gel-forming mixtures corresponds to the case of coagulation of a colloidal solution by mixtures of electrolytes.

Freundlich, Weiser, Dhar, Mukherjee and others have studied the coagulation of colloidal solutions by mixtures of electrolytes and have found that various factors, such as hydration of the ions and of the colloid, the displacement of adsorption of one ion by the other, the variation of the electric charge on the colloid, come into play.

The results of the present investigation on the influence of other electrolytes in the presence of sodium acetate on the coagulation of the silicic acid sol indicate the order of coagulating power as follows:—

both in the alkaline and in the acid media. The state of aggregation of the gel particles is also in the same order. This is in confirmation with the observation of Pappada (*loc. cit.*) who found the order $\text{Cs} > \text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$ as regards their coagulating power on the silicic acid sol.

It is also evident from the above results that the influence of the anions on the gel-formation is in the order $\text{Cl} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$. The state of aggregation of the gel particles also follows the same order. Dokan's (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 155) recent work on the swelling of agar-agar also suggests that the state of aggregation of the gel colloids and coherence of their frame work is influenced by the nature of the electrolytes. To examine the behaviour of these ions further, gels were prepared only from sodium silicate ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}, 2.38\text{SiO}_2$) and NH_4Cl , NH_4NO_3 , and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and the following results were obtained for the time of setting measured by Fleming's method.

It may be mentioned here that very good gels can be obtained easily, by using almost any ammonium salt instead of ammonium acetate.

TABLE III.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4$ per cent.

Strength.	NH_4Cl	NH_4NO_3	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
	t	t	t
0.5N	17 min. 20 sec.	57 min.	4 hrs.
0.6N	4 .. 40 ..	11½ ..	28½ min.
0.7N	1 .. 20 ..	3½ ..	7½ ..

TABLE III—*contd.*Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=5$ per cent.

	NH_4Cl	NH_4NO_3	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
<i>Strength.</i>	t	t	t
0.7N	1 min 45 sec.	5 min.	14 min.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=8$ per cent.

0.6N	1 min. 10 sec.	3 min.	6 min.
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These results confirm the conclusion arrived at above that the power of decreasing the time of setting is in the order $\text{Cl} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$.

The acetates seem to have a marked coagulating influence. Werner (*J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1920, 9, 501) found that the acetates of the various metals had the greatest congealing effect on the silicic acid sol. It appears from similarity of the results obtained in this investigation with those obtained by Werner, Graham, Pappada and others (*loc. cit.*) that gel-formation is really a case of coagulation of the colloidal silicic acid by electrolytes. The great effect of the acetates in the present case may also be due to a repression of the H- and OH-ions, thus making the silicic acid sol formed in the gel-forming mixtures of sodium silicate and acetic acid comparatively unstable.

The behaviour of sodium sulphate in being a poor coagulant is rather anomalous. In the acid region where the silicic acid particles are positively charged, the sulphate ion should be a better coagulant than the other monovalent anions. This observation is similar to that pointed out in Part II that with sulphuric acid the time of setting is greater in the acidic as well as alkaline media than with hydrochloric acid in mixtures of the same p_H . It is probable that this is a case of ionic antagonism.

Kruyt and Postma (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1925, 44, 765) have found that large quantities of OH- and Cl-ions are adsorbed by silicic acid whether positively or negatively charged. The better congealing effect of the chloride than the nitrate, perhaps, depends upon the preferential adsorption of the Cl-ions. The Cl-ions do not, it appears, stabilise the silicic acid sol in the alkaline medium, as would

be expected from the ordinary laws of coagulation. OH-Ions also behave in a similar manner, that is, instead of stabilising the negatively charged sol, the slightest excess of them causes a turbidity and favours strong flocculation or complete gelatinisation by other electrolytes.

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